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Abstract

The 22nd International Nondestructive Testing and Evaluation of Wood Symposium was hosted by the Université Laval in Quebec City, Canada, May 24–27, 2022. This symposium was a forum for those involved in nondestructive testing and evaluation (NDT/NDE) of wood and brought together many international researchers, NDT/NDE users, suppliers, representatives from various government agencies, and other groups to share research results, products, and technology for evaluating a wide range of wood products, including standing trees, logs, structural lumber, engineered wood products, and wood structures. Networking among participants encouraged international collaborative efforts and fostered the implementation of NDT/NDE technologies around the world. A special on-line session was conducted to accommodate individuals who could not attend in-person due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. The technical content of the 22nd symposium is captured in these proceedings. Full-length, in-depth technical papers for most of the oral presentations, along with abstracts for all the oral and poster presentations, are published herein. The papers were not peer reviewed and are reproduced here as they were submitted by the authors.

Keywords: Nondestructive evaluation, nondestructive testing, wood properties, wood products, logs, trees, wood structures

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Contents

Preface.....	3
General Session.....	5
Session 1—Nondestructive Characterization of Wood and Wood-Based Materials	18
Session 2—In-Forest Wood Quality Assessments	71
Session 3—NDE for Urban Trees.....	139
Session 4—NDE of Sawm Logs for Optimal Utilization.....	191
Session 5—Advanced Grading Technologies for Solid Wood and Engineered Wood Products	209
Session 6—Condition Assessment of Historic Wood Artifacts and Structures	252
Mixed Session (Online).....	270
Poster Session	322

Prediction of Tensile Modulus of Elasticity from Longitudinal and Transverse Natural Frequencies in Hardwood Species

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Abstract

Currently, most of structural timber in Europe is graded with C classes, obtained from bending tests; however, many engineered wood products require the grading in T classes, from tensile tests. The increasing demand of wood for structures leads to the need of studying new timber species, mainly focused on both high strength capacity and/or fast-grown criteria. Then, the objective of this study is to evaluate the stiffness properties of different hardwood species by both non-destructive testing and tensile tests according to EN 408. Three high-, medium- and low- density hardwood species from Spain, named *Eucalyptus globulus*, *Fagus sylvatica* and *Populus x euramericana*, respectively, were studied and compared with a well-known and more commonly used species in structures in Europe (*Pinus sylvestris*). The first step was the measurement of both longitudinal and transverse vibration modes, following the standard ASTM C215-2, in 30 specimens of each species to estimate the dynamic moduli of elasticity obtained from: i) the longitudinal natural frequency; and ii) from the first, third and fifth transverse natural frequencies, using the Timoshenko beam theory. The second step was the comparison between the dynamic moduli of elasticity and the static modulus of elasticity in tension. The results showed different stiffness/density relationships for the four studied species, being poplar and pine grouped in the lower values and Eucalyptus in the higher values. Poplar showed a behaviour like a coniferous species. The values for dynamic modulus obtained from transverse vibration were higher than that obtained from longitudinal vibration for the medium- and low-density species. However, the Eucalyptus globulus, being the one with the highest values for both density and stiffness properties, showed a lower value.

Keywords: NDT, hardwood, vibration analysis

Introduction

General information

Currently we are experiencing an increased demand for timber and timber products worldwide (Dangel, 2016). The increasing demand of wood for structures leads to the need of studying new timber species, mainly focused on both high strength capacity and/or fast-grown criteria. Fast-growing criterium is mainly associated to softwood species and high strength capacity to hardwoods. There are species which combine

both of these qualities, such as, *Eucalyptus* sps. (Lara Bocanegra 2017; Vega 2020), among others. In Europe, softwood species are mainly graded in C classes and hardwood species in D classes (for bending) and T classes for tension (softwoods), these classes are defined by the standard EN 338:2016. Currently there are no classes defined for hardwoods tested in tension, even if the current criteria allow hardwoods to be classified as T classes if the mean density is lower than 600 kg/m^3 . Thus, medium- and high- density hardwoods cannot be assigned to strength classes in tension. On the other hand, standard for the production of Glulam beams (EN 14080:2013), proposes a method to calculate the properties of Glulam beams based on the tensile properties of lamellas.

Therefore, the objective of this study is to evaluate the stiffness properties of three different Spanish high-, medium- and low- density hardwood species (*Eucalyptus globulus*, *Fagus sylvatica* and *Populus x euramericana*, respectively) obtained from longitudinal and transversal natural frequencies and from experimental tensile tests, comparing their potential grading yield with a well-known species (*Pinus sylvestris*).

Methodology

Four different species were studied, three high-, medium- and low- density hardwood species and one softwood species: Blue gum (*Eucalyptus globulus*), Beech (*Fagus sylvatica*), Poplar (*Populus x euramericana*) and Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) respectively. For each species, 30 specimens were tested.

Non-Destructive Testing

Vibration measurements were carried out using two different configurations, longitudinal and transversal, following the guidance of ASTM C215-19. In the longitudinal setup, the pickup accelerometer was placed in one end and the impulse given by a hammer was done in the other end. In the transverse setup, the supports were placed at a given distance from the end (matching the vibration node), the pickup was placed on one end and the impact was driven in the centre of the beam. The acceleration was registered in steps of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}$ over a time frame of 8 s. Measurements of moisture content were made with a handheld xylohygrometer (EN 13183-2: 2002). Mass and dimensions of each specimen were recorded. The set up for the non-destructive test is shown in Figure 1.

A pickup unidirectional accelerometer was used (PCB 352C33) connected to an USB oscilloscope (DS1M12 from Connective Peripherals). The signal is then registered and processed in a numerical analysis software, obtaining the Fast Fourier Transform.

Figure 1: NDT setup for: a) longitudinal vibration, b) transverse vibration

Frequency analysis

Using the Fast Fourier Transform function from MATLAB, the FFT for each time-acceleration signal was obtained. For the longitudinal vibration modes, the frequency of the first longitudinal vibration mode was recorded. For transversal mode the frequencies for the first, third and fifth vibration modes were obtained. An example of the obtained FFT for transverse vibration is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: FFT of a transverse vibration signal for a Beech specimen

Dynamic elastic modulus determination

Two different analyses were used for the determination of the dynamic elastic modulus. The first one was a direct method, using the frequency of the first longitudinal vibration mode (1).

$$E_{dyn,L} = (2f_L L)^2 \rho \quad (1)$$

Where $E_{dyn,L}$ is the dynamic elastic modulus obtained from longitudinal frequency, the length L and the density ρ . The second approach involves optimizing the relationship for the elastic modulus and the shear modulus using the equations given by Majkut (Majkut 2009) for a beam using the Timoshenko beam theory.

Destructive Testing

Tension tests were carried out obtaining tension strength and elastic modulus. Protocol defined by EN 408:2011+A1:2012 was followed Density was determined following the procedure described in EN 408:2011+A1:2012 (Figure 2). Moisture content for destructive testing was determined following the oven dry method described in EN 13183-1:2002+AC:2003. Mass and dimensions were registered at this time as well.

Figure 2: Tensile test configuration (EN 408:2011+A1:2012)

Where h is the width of the specimen. To calculate the static elastic modulus, two extensometers were placed at each side of the specimen as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Tensile test of a *Pinus sylvestris* specimen

Results

Sample properties

The properties of the samples studied for each species is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the sample data

Species	Value	$E_{dyn,L}$ (N/mm ²)	$E_{dyn,T}$ (N/mm ²)	$f_{t,0}$ (N/mm ²)	$E_{t,0}$ (N/mm ²)	Density (Kg/m ³)
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	Mean	13287	13333	36.0	13072	548
	CoV (%)	19	20	29.0	18	11
<i>Populus x euramericana</i>	Mean	10813	11197	41.1	10698	455
	CoV (%)	16	17	36	15	10
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	Mean	14632	14845	64.7	13036	717
	CoV (%)	12	12	26	10	5
<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i>	Mean	20890	20688	75.1	20418	861
	CoV (%)	17	18	30	17	9

Where $E_{dyn,T}$ is the dynamic modulus of elasticity obtained from transversal frequencies, $f_{t,0}$ the tensile strength and $E_{t,0}$ is the static modulus of elasticity.

It was observed the different range of densities among the hardwood group, ranging from 455 to 861 Kg/m³, the same tendency was noted for the rest of the properties.

NDT testing vs. Grade Determining Properties

In this section the results the relationship between the non-destructive testing results and the grade determining properties are presented (Tensile strength, Elastic modulus and Density). In Figure 5 the relationship between tensile strength and both dynamic modulus of elasticity is shown. The results showed a normal correlation for pine, but the correlation was worse for the hardwoods (for eucalyptus the correlation coefficient was as low as 0.16 for the longitudinal dynamic elastic modulus). In hardwoods the transversal dynamic elastic modulus showed a minimal improvement compared to the longitudinal one.

Figure 5: Relationships between tensile strength and dynamic modulus of elasticity

The relationship between dynamic and static elastic modulus is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Relationships between tensile static elastic modulus and dynamic modulus of elasticity

Despite having lower correlation when compared to softwood, the dynamic elastic modulus showed to be a good prediction parameter for the static elastic modulus in hardwoods. The correlation coefficient did not change significantly among the hardwood group.

In figure 7 it is shown the relationship between density and dynamic elastic modulus.

Figure 7: Relationships between density and dynamic elastic modulus

The density showed a normal correlation with the dynamic elastic modulus of elasticity for Pine and Poplar (low density hardwood), for the higher density hardwoods the correlation was as low as 0.13 (Beech).

Conclusions and future works

There is a high potential for the use of hardwoods for structural purposes. The growth rate of these species along with the high mechanical properties imply that they can be used to increase sustainability.

Both non-destructive methods studied showed similar prediction values, however, the computational cost of calculating the transversal modulus of elasticity is high and an optimization study is needed.

The transversal analysis also provides the shear modulus, static test needs to be performed to verify this method of prediction.

For hardwoods the dynamic modulus of elasticity is not a good predictor of tensile strength, specially for high density ones. Other non-destructive parameters such as fibre deviation should be studied.

The dynamic modulus of elasticity (for both methods) is a good method to predict the static elastic modulus despite the difference in species and densities.

For high density hardwoods, the dynamic elastic modulus showed poor correlations. It shows acceptable levels for low density hardwoods.

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